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Fire Performance of Biopolymers Recovered from Waste Aerobic Granular Sludges

NK. Kim¹, RJT. Lin¹, D. Bhattacharyya¹, MCM van Loosdrecht², YM Lin^{2*}

¹ Mechanical Engineering Department, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

² Department of Biotechnology, Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands

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Content

- **Introduction**
- **Experimental**
- **Results and Discussion**
- **Conclusions**

Combustion Cycle / Flame Retardation

(Mouritz, 2006)

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Sample Preparation

Extracellular Polymer Extraction

- ALE polymer..
- Activated sludge polymer..

Biopolymer Coated Flax Fabric

- Flax fabric (2 x 2 twill weave, 145 g/m² areal density)

Characterisation Methods

Thermogravimetric Analysis

- 6 ~ 7 mg sample
- 10 °C/min heating rate
- Final temperature: 800 °C

Vertical Burn Test

(Code of Federal Regulation 25.853)

Test chamber

Testing Set-up

Burner Flame time (s)	12	60
Avg. Flame time (s)	< 15	< 15
Avg. Burn length (mm)	203.2 (8 inch)	152.4 (6 inch)
Avg. Drip extinguishing (s)	< 5	< 3

Vertical burn test schematic diagram
(Federal Aviation Regulations)

Cone Calorimeter

Cone heater

Sample

Oxygen (paramagnetic) and CO/CO₂ (IR) analyser

- Bench-scale test to measure fire reaction properties under heat flux
- ISO 5660 standard
- 50 kW/m² heat flux
- Fire reaction properties
 - Time to ignition (TTI)
 - Peak heat release rate (PHRR)
 - Total heat release (THR)
 - Total smoke production (TSP)

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Thermal Stability: Extracellular Polymers

Sample	Amount of residue at 800 °C (wt%)
ALE polymer	38.3
Activated sludge polymer	39.6
Wool	24.1
Ammonium polyphosphate	29

Thermal Stability: Biopolymer coated Flax

FAR 12s Vertical Burn Test

Neat Flax

**Activated sludge
coated flax**

ALE coated flax

Cone Calorimeter Test (ALE Polymer)

Before Test

After Test

Specimen	ALE-1	ALE-2	ALE-3	Mean
Peak heat release rate (kW/m ²)	146.7	203.03	139.84	163.19
Time to peak heat release rate (s)	25	35	25	28.3
Total heat release (MJ/m ²)	11.2	7.0	8.2	8.8
CO yield (kg/kg)	0.0363	0.0325	0.0387	0.0358
CO ₂ yield (kg/kg)	1.11	1.26	1.26	1.21

Conclusions

- The extracellular biopolymer was successfully extracted from activated and aerobic granular sludge.
- Both activated sludge and aerobic granular biopolymers showed effective char formation due to their protein and phosphate components.
- FTIR or SEM images results.. Phosphate?.
- The self-extinguishment of the biopolymer coated flax fabric indicated the fire-resistant behaviour of the biopolymer substance.